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Elevated Engagement: Creative Strategies and Pedagogical Enhancement for Improving Science Literacy Among Filipino Science Teachers on the Island of Panay

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Abstract

Objective: To assess the use of creative strategies and the level of pedagogical enhancement among Filipino science teachers on the Island of Panay and to explore their relationship in promoting science literacy. **Method:** The research design is a descriptive survey using a researcher-made questionnaire validated by five experts. The questionnaire was divided into two sections: Section 1 focused on creative strategies, and Section 2 on pedagogical enhancement. The researchers used the mean, standard deviation, and Spearman's rho. **Findings:** The respondents' profiles showed that 40 elementary teachers, 32 junior high school (JHS) teachers, and 28 senior high school teachers participated in this study. The creative strategies mean score ranged from 1.72 to 2.31 and was interpreted as sometimes. These creative strategies are role-playing, concept mapping, world cloud guessing, and classroom opinion. While pedagogical enhancement was rated very often, with mean scores from 2.23 to 2.89. When grouped by educational qualification, years of service, sex, and school type, creative was rated sometimes, with mean scores ranging from 1.95 to 2.11, while pedagogical enhancement was rated very often, with mean scores ranging from 2.47 to 2.58. There was no significant relationship between creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement ($r = 0.123$, $p = 0.223$) in terms of teachers' awareness. This implies that both variables operate independently in classroom practice. Findings suggest a gap between teachers' awareness and actual implementation of creative strategies despite strong pedagogical practices. **Novelty:** Scientific literacy largely depends on teachers' ability to deliver instruction effectively. Educators serve as key agents of learning, responsible for ensuring that knowledge is conveyed in meaningful and efficient ways using creative strategies and innovative approaches. In this context, the study underscores the importance of providing targeted professional development, sustained support, and specialized training to enhance the integration of creativity in science instruction.

Keywords: Basic Education; Creative Strategies; Pedagogical Enhancement; Science Literacy; Science Teacher

1 Introduction

In the Philippines, science literacy remains a significant concern, despite ongoing efforts to improve learners' academic performance. Around 1.8 million Filipino learners have benefited from the Department of Education (DepEd) 's efforts, with support from the national government, to strengthen literacy and communication skills. But this effort shows no effect, as many are still struggling with reading proficiency, especially in science, where understanding complex concepts is essential. Thus, elementary teachers are encouraged to engage in remedial classes, highlighting persistent gaps in learners' comprehension and engagement. One study found that the most effective way to implement remedial reading programs is to extend sessions, use effective teaching strategies, have well-trained teachers, involve parents, and use technology. Linkages among stakeholders are key to success⁽¹⁾. A reading program at an early age helps improve science literacy by boosting comprehension, vocabulary, and analytical skills. This helps learners better understand and apply scientific concepts. Literacy in science and scientific literacy are not the same, but are interconnected. Literacy in science is about cultivating individuals' understanding of science content. Scientific literacy is about understanding scientific concepts, phenomena, and processes and the ability to apply them to daily life⁽²⁾. This helps students learn science and affects our daily lives.

Also, DepEd promotes creative and innovative teaching approaches to improve science literacy that cater to learners with below-average skills. The science curriculum in the Philippines has undergone various reforms during the implementation of the K12 Basic Education programs. The spiral progression is one of the key factors of the new curriculum in 2012, but it faces various challenges and criticism. One study reviews the spiral approach of the K12 Science Curriculum. The findings show that integrate contents and process skills. It also promotes curiosity through real-life context. They adopt a learner-centered progressive approach. But this approach faces implementation challenges⁽³⁾. The spiral progression approach is ineffective due to shallow content coverage, unprepared teachers, a scarcity of teaching materials, and unresolved learning gaps across all levels.

Furthermore, these challenges were further intensified during the pandemic. The teachers struggle to deliver inquiry-based science education in an online learning environment. Limited internet access and a lack of technological resources are among the factors contributing to ineffective online learning. Thus, students become unmotivated, which affects the quality of instruction. Technology-enhanced learning emerges as an alternative way to continue learning, but its effectiveness in improving science outcomes remains a debate. This is confirmed by one study, which found that students faced several challenges during online learning. These barriers are limited access to gadgets and computers, limited engagement, difficulties with self-management, content challenges, and stress. Thus, the findings suggest the need for better-designed, more engaging online science education⁽⁴⁾. Most countries worldwide are unprepared for the pandemic. Schools are not ready, and teachers are unaware of what to do. Thus, the entire education system suffers a lot.

Previous studies suggest that creative strategies, such as art integration, project-based learning, and hands-on activities, can enhance students' sense of purpose and commitment. A study of integrating the arts into primary school teaching, but the results show that sustaining it is limited. This is due to weak interdisciplinary collaboration, inadequate leadership support, and limited partnerships. Further, there would be strong cooperation between schools and cultural institutions⁽⁵⁾. In high school, this study confirmed that continuous participation in art-based programs enhances academic performance, creativity, and cultural engagement. This participation also motivates students to pursue college⁽⁶⁾. Also, both project-based and creative learning help improve engagement and creativity. But challenges such as curriculum constraints, time, resources, and students' reading skills. To achieve the main goal of arts integration, incorporating real-world tasks, opinions, and boldness to enhance creative thinking is recommended⁽⁷⁾. Art integration into science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEAM) increases creativity, understanding, and engagement with abstract concepts. This also helps improve critical thinking, problem-solving, and real-world application of knowledge.

As a result, many studies concentrate on general academic achievement rather than science literacy. In countries like the Philippines, there is always limited contextualization. Educational challenges are shaped by resource scarcity and the diverse types of learners. In addition, research on creativity and pedagogy is conducted separately; no studies explore their combined influence on science teaching. Empirical facts on how creative strategies link to pedagogical enhancement among basic education curriculum, particularly in the local context of the Island of Panay, Philippines. One study explores how creative learning becomes significant in children's education; the findings revealed that teachers who are artists continue to support creative learning even when policies are restricted⁽⁸⁾. This shows that teachers who are into the arts always integrate them into their teaching. They always value the importance of the arts in science because this helps students understand scientific ideas more clearly. Furthermore, the use of the arts in the science curriculum makes abstract ideas easier and more meaningful.

A study conducted in underserved communities facing significant challenges, such as limited teaching materials, revealed that these areas are often economically disadvantaged. In response, many teachers become innovators, developing localized instructional materials, providing take-home activities, and adapting their teaching approaches to suit learners' needs. The findings highlight that creativity, combined with resilience and adequate support for context-based education, is essential⁽⁹⁾.

These conditions continue to challenge educators, underscoring the importance of creative strategies in enhancing pedagogical practices.

To address this gap, this study aims to assess the use of creative strategies and the level of pedagogical enhancement among Filipino science teachers on the Island of Panay and to explore their relationship in promoting science literacy. Hence, the novelty lies in its integrated approach, combining creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement in the science curriculum. Unlike prior studies that treat the concepts separately, this research provides a localized and context-sensitive analysis of Filipino science classrooms. Based on the findings, this research aims to inform curriculum developers and teachers in support of innovative and effective science teaching practices.

2 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

This study used a descriptive-correlational research design because it permits the researchers to explain and investigate existing conditions without manipulating the variables. This is appropriate for exploring patterns, relationships, and trends among variables connected to teachers’ creative strategies and pedagogical engagement practices in science education as they naturally occur in perspective.

2.2 Research Instruments

The study utilized a researcher-developed instrument derived from various literature sources. Initially, 100 active learning techniques were identified and presented to science teachers at the elementary and secondary levels within the Department of Education (DepEd), who were asked to indicate which strategies they commonly use in the science curriculum. Based on their responses, the researchers narrowed the list to 14 creative learning strategies that effectively support science teaching and learning. To enhance pedagogy, the researchers also compiled approximately 50 related items from existing sources. These were presented to the same group of participants, who then identified the 14 most frequently employed strategies in the science curriculum.

Table 1 presents the various creative strategies and pedagogical enhancements used by science teachers in Northern Iloilo, Philippines. These items will serve as instruments for the current research study.

Table 1. Creative Strategies and Pedagogical Enhancements as Research Instrument of this Study

Creative Strategies	Pedagogical Enhancement
Brainstorming	Exposure to knowledge
Concept Mapping	Constructive criticism
Role Playing	Repetition and revision
Word Cloud Guessing	Problem-based Learning
Exam Evaluation	Creativity
Picture Prompt	Motivation
Classroom Opinion Polls	Exposure
Word of the Day	Practical Activities
Photo Homework	Collaborative Learning
True or False?	Positive Relationship
Think-Pair-Share	Relevance of Content
Draw Your Partner	Communication
Student Videos	Inquiry-based Learning
Scrapbook Selection	Integrate Learning

2.3 Research Respondents

The respondents of this study were 100 science teachers from elementary, junior high school (JHS), and senior high schools from the Island of Panay, Philippines. These respondents were selected based on their availability during the visit and were willing to participate in this research study.

2.4 Research Procedure

Data collection was conducted from 2022 to 2023 across selected Department of Education (DepEd) schools on the island of Panay. The researchers personally administered and retrieved the questionnaires to ensure a higher response rate, facilitate immediate clarification of queries, and maintain the accuracy of responses. This hands-on approach also helped establish rapport with participants, thereby improving the reliability of the data gathered. To further strengthen the study's rigor, a validation process was conducted in 2025. During this phase, the collected data and research instruments were carefully reviewed to ensure accuracy, completeness, and consistency. Any ambiguities or discrepancies were addressed prior to data analysis, reinforcing the overall credibility and trustworthiness of the findings.

2.5 Internal Control and Data Validation

Several internal control measures were implemented to secure data quality and reliability. A pilot test of instructions before full deployment at selected schools in Northern Iloilo, Philippines. After the pilot test, in which 14 categories were selected for each concept, expert validation was employed. These experts were from state universities and colleges (SUCs) that handle science courses in the College of Education, to avoid biases and other external and internal factors that could affect the results. Also, the researchers used a consistency check during data encoding and cleaning to ensure accurate results.

2.6 Data Analysis

For data analysis, mean, standard deviation, and Spearman's Rho correlation were employed. These statistical tools were selected to describe central tendencies, variability, and relationships among variables. A statistician was asked to validate the results using statistical tools.

2.7 Ethical Considerations

The researchers followed ethical standards to ensure that all individuals participating in this research were protected. Prior to conducting the study, approval from various key officials was obtained. Participants are volunteers, and informed consent was secured from all the participants. No personal data was collected, and confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained. The data collected was used solely for academic purposes. Participants were free to withdraw at any time without penalty. Honesty, transparency, and accuracy were maintained throughout the research process.

3 Research and Discussions

Table 2 presents the detailed profile of the study participants. The study involved 100 purposively selected respondents

By grade level, 40% were elementary teachers, 32% were junior high school (JHS) teachers, and 28% were senior high school (SHS) teachers. This indicates that many are interested in understanding what the creative standard is and its relationship to pedagogical engagement. In terms of years of service, the majority were relatively young in the profession: 74% had served for 1-10 years, 19% for 11-20 years, and 7% for 21 years or more. The results of the profiling show that this potential to encourage the implementation of creative strategies in the science curriculum is strong, as many are still young and passionate about improving students' scientific literacy. Regarding educational attainment, 16% held bachelor's degrees, 79% had completed or were pursuing master's degrees, and 5% had either completed or were pursuing doctoral programs. This distribution reflects the strong encouragement for teachers to pursue continuing professional development, supported by the Department of Education's scholarship initiatives and programs offered by other public and private institutions. But this is a call, especially for those teaching in elementary grades, to pursue graduate programs in science, not management. Regarding sex, 43% of respondents were male, while 57% were female. For school type, 38% were from small schools and 62% from large schools. The participants represented four provinces in Western Visayas: Iloilo, Aklan, Antique, and Capiz.

During the pandemic, science was one of the most affected subjects in the basic education curriculum. Studies showed that science learners struggled during the pandemic, even though science has become an exciting subject in recent years. Teachers are given standard science curriculum materials even if these are not aligned with learners' skills and capacities⁽¹⁰⁾. Thus, many science teachers are interested in participating in research activities to improve their knowledge and skills.

Table 3 shows how often science teachers at the elementary, junior high, and senior high school levels in Panay Island use different creative teaching strategies.

Generally, the results imply that most of the creative strategies identified are described as sometimes across all grade levels, with mean scores of 1.72 and 2.30 for elementary grades, 1.81 and 2.13 for JHS, and 1.91 and 2.31 for SHS. This suggests that

Table 2. Profiles of science teachers on the Island of Panay, Philippines

	Frequency	Percent
Grade Level		
Elementary	40	40%
Junior High School	32	32%
Senior High School	28	28%
Years in Service		
10 years and below	74	74%
11 – 20 years	19	19%
21 years and above	7	7%
Educational Qualifications		
Bachelor’s Degree	16	16%
Master’s Degree	79	79%
Doctorate Degree	5	5%
Sex		
Male	43	43%
Female	57	57%
Type of School		
Small	38	38%
Big	62	62%

Table 3. Creative strategies utilized by science teachers on the Island of Panay, Philippines

Item	Elementary		Junior High School		Senior High School	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Brainstorming	2.08	Sometimes	1.87	Sometimes	2.06	Sometimes
Concept Mapping	2.25	Sometimes	2.13	Sometimes	2.25	Sometimes
Role Playing	2.28	Sometimes	2.03	Sometimes	2.31	Sometimes
Word Cloud Guessing	2.30	Sometimes	1.94	Sometimes	2.20	Sometimes
Exam Evaluation	1.48	Not at all	1.59	Not at all	1.66	Not at all
Picture Prompt	1.83	Sometimes	1.91	Sometimes	1.91	Sometimes
Classroom Opinion Polls	2.20	Sometimes	2.03	Sometimes	2.20	Sometimes
Word of the Day	2.10	Sometimes	1.81	Sometimes	2.02	Sometimes
Photo Homework	1.63	Not at all	1.56	Not at all	1.58	Not at all
True or False?	2.30	Sometimes	2.03	Sometimes	2.22	Sometimes
Think-Pair-Share	1.72	Sometimes	1.94	Sometimes	1.84	Sometimes
Draw Your Partner	2.05	Sometimes	1.81	Sometimes	2.05	Sometimes
Student Videos	2.12	Sometimes	1.97	Sometimes	2.16	Sometimes
Scrapbook Selection	2.17	Sometimes	1.91	Sometimes	2.11	Sometimes

science teachers are aware of these strategies but do not often apply them. They are not consistently integrating these creative strategies into everyday teaching. One study found that teachers recognize aspects of creativity; however, they are uncertain about how to apply them in practice, particularly in science teaching and learning. They are often used in inquiry- and project-based learning, but a deeper aspect of creativity, such as hypothesis-making and imagination, remains weak. Thus, the study highlights the need to encourage teachers to participate in training and workshops to effectively promote creative thinking in the science curriculum. Support from school heads and adequate resources are also suggested⁽¹¹⁾. Thus, the current findings revealed that science teachers in the Island of Panay, Philippines, should be urged to pursue various professional development opportunities in creative strategies to help them implement innovations effectively. During in-service training for teachers, creative strategies must be among the topics. Also, support from the school and the teaching materials must be provided.

Among the items, role-playing, concept mapping, word cloud guessing, classroom opinion rolls, and true-or-false activities have comparatively higher mean scores. This indicates that these creative strategies are commonly used by science teachers in basic education curricula. These strategies might be appealing to teachers because they are easy to implement and more engaging for students. Students who were taught through role-play achieved higher scores and showed greater creativity, suggesting that role-playing effectively enhances both conceptual understanding and creative skills⁽¹²⁾. According to one result, concept mapping is often used as an instructional approach to help learners organize ideas. The strategies also improve understanding and academic performance in science⁽¹³⁾. Much research has confirmed that creativity assists critical thinking, collaboration, and leadership. Thus, as future teachers, the college may support training to improve competencies⁽¹⁴⁾. Thus, at NISU, Ajuy Campus, Ajuy, Iloilo, Philippines, aside from regular academic loads, various training and workshops to enhance the creativity of pre-service teachers were facilitated and organized to equip them to become effective and efficient future science educators.

In the science curriculum, hands-on activities play a vital role in students’ science experiences, but due to a lack of teaching and learning materials, teachers rely on lectures. The lack of adequate training for teachers to become innovative and creative is one of the main reasons they lack the knowledge to improve the science curriculum. One study confirmed that a lack of training leads to a lack of confidence and struggles in managing the science classroom. This study emphasizes the importance of training to upgrade students’ engagement and scientific literacy⁽¹⁵⁾. Many of these teachers have attended various training programs in the past, but the scarcity of teaching materials and the lack of financial support to buy their own materials hinder their vision of providing quality science education. This is a call for the national government to allocate more funds for teaching materials. Even though many are using recycled materials, you still need to buy some other materials, such as glue, scissors, and any additional art materials.

Table 4 presents the level of pedagogical enhancement among science teachers across elementary, junior high school, and senior high school levels in the Island of Panay.

Table 4. Pedagogical enhancement of science teachers on the Island of Panay, Philippines

Items	Elementary		Junior High School		Senior High School	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Exposure to knowledge	2.72	Very Often	2.78	Very Often	2.89	Very Often
Constructive criticism	2.52	Very Often	2.34	Very Often	2.64	Very Often
Repetition and revision	2.23	Often	2.66	Very Often	2.82	Very Often
Problem-based Learning	2.40	Very Often	2.59	Very Often	2.64	Very Often
Creativity	2.40	Very Often	2.53	Very Often	2.64	Very Often
Motivation	2.62	Very Often	2.44	Very Often	2.57	Very Often
Exposure	2.45	Very Often	2.50	Very Often	2.64	Very Often
Practical Activities	2.50	Very Often	2.44	Very Often	2.61	Very Often
Collaborative Learning	2.57	Very Often	2.75	Very Often	2.79	Very Often
Positive Relationship	2.52	Very Often	2.66	Very Often	2.75	Very Often
Relevance of Content	2.48	Very Often	2.47	Very Often	2.50	Very Often
Communication	2.33	Very Often	2.44	Very Often	2.54	Very Often
Inquiry-based Learning	2.43	Very Often	2.56	Very Often	2.46	Very Often
Integrate Learning	2.45	Very Often	2.66	Very Often	2.61	Very Often

Almost all indicators are reported as very often; this suggests that most of the identified pedagogical enhancements were used by science teachers at all levels. Among the strategies, exposure to knowledge had the highest mean score, especially to SHS, at 2.89. Also, collaborative learning was highly practiced, with mean scores of 2.75 for JHS and 2.79 for SHS. And a positive relationship with mean scores of 2.66 for JHS and 2.79 for SHS. The results indicate that teachers value teamwork and a supportive learning environment. Another notable result is in repetition and revision: in elementary grade, it is often rated with a mean score of 2.23, but in JHS and SHS, it is very often rated with mean scores of 2.66 and 2.82, respectively. The rest of the items are rated very often. In addition, the results showed that the mean SHS scores were high. But the differences across all levels were minimal. The results showed that the effective learning strategies are applied in the basic science curriculum. This indicates that science teachers in the Island of Panay, Philippines, are commonly enhancing their teaching to improve students’ understanding. One study confirms that collaborative learning is commonly used by science teachers in JHS.

To back up the findings, one study shows that while Science teachers excel in pedagogy, classroom management, and teaching strategies, their content knowledge is basic. Students have low basic Science skills but moderate integrated skills. Teachers’

effective strategies are closely linked to student learning, underscoring the need for professional development to strengthen teachers’ content knowledge and better support students’ scientific skill development⁽¹⁶⁾. Many experts explained that studying pedagogy can enhance every curriculum. Pedagogy can be defined as the teaching-learning process for children, which can be extended to informal settings outside educational institutions⁽¹⁷⁾. In addition, a study exploring pedagogical decision-making by science teachers in addressing pedagogical issues from their perspective found that seeking advice from supervisors and senior teachers is the main factor in becoming effective and efficient teachers⁽¹⁸⁾. In the science curriculum, pedagogical engagement is important because it helps determine how science is taught. Science ideas are abstract and complex; thus, effective teaching helps students understand them more easily. When pedagogy is enhanced, teachers can use a range of approaches, such as inquiry-based learning, laboratory work, and real-world scenarios. This permits students to think critically, ask questions, and actively participate rather than memorize facts.

Table 5 shows how teachers use creative strategies and how these relate to pedagogical enhancement across different groups.

Table 5. Creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement in terms of four categories

Category	Creative Strategies		Pedagogical Enhancement	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
Educational Qualification				
Bachelor’s Degree	1.99	Sometimes	2.52	Very Often
Master’s Degree	2.02	Sometimes	2.54	Very Often
Doctorate Degree	2.46	Always	2.72	Very Often
Total	2.94	Always	2.54	Very Often
Years in Service				
10 years and below	2.04	Sometimes	2.53	Very Often
11 – 20 years	2.06	Sometimes	2.54	Very Often
Above 20 years	1.99	Sometimes	2.72	Very Often
Total	2.04	Sometimes	2.54	Very Often
Sex				
Male	1.95	Sometimes	2.49	Very Often
Female	2.11	Sometimes	2.58	Very Often
Total	2.04	Sometimes	2.54	Very Often
School Type				
Small School	1.95	Sometimes	2.49	Very Often
Big School	2.08	Sometimes	2.59	Very Often
Total	2.04	Sometimes	2.47	Very Often

The results proved that creative strategies are operated only sometimes (mean score of 2.04) and that pedagogical enhancement is practiced often (mean score of 2.54). This indicates that teachers wanted to improve their teaching approaches but were inconsistent in applying creative strategies. When classified as an educational qualification, doctorate degree holders embrace creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement, with mean scores of 2.46 (always) and 2.72 (strong), respectively. The results imply that as you go higher in education, your support for innovative practices becomes more advanced. But both bachelor’s and master’s still show high in creative strategies and sometimes in pedagogical improvement. This suggests that, regardless of educational attainment, both creative strategies and pedagogical enhancements are important for improving science performance. Similarly, in years in service, creative strategies were rated sometimes, whereas pedagogical enhancement was very often rated. The results highlight that experience strengthens teaching quality more than creativity. For sex and school types, there were minimal differences. Females in big schools showed slightly higher means, 2.11 and 2.08, and were described as sometimes, and the same patterns with pedagogical enhancement of 2.58 and 2.59 and interpreted as very often. Thus, science teachers were very consistent in saying they want to improve their teaching but often need to use creative strategies.

Those early years teachers have already been using creative strategies to enhance science teaching and learning. Also, the different backgrounds of the respondents in this study don’t affect students’ performance, but the integration of innovative approaches was one of the factors that helped students increase their performance in the subject areas. With the findings, the suggestion was to conduct training and workshops on creative approaches and effective strategies. Instead of relying on the engagement to improve students’ performance⁽¹⁹⁾. In addition, one study confirmed that demographic factors, such as

gender or educational qualifications, do not influence teachers’ ideas of professional development; for instance, attending training may work better for secondary teachers, or teachers with higher degrees may help them improve and advance their teaching strategies. Thus, when allowing science teachers to attend training, proper assessment is recommended to guarantee the training is beneficial to them. Mentorship must also be recommended to ensure sustainability⁽²⁰⁾. The need assessment must be prioritized to ensure that these teacher training courses or workshops are relevant and important.

In addition, science teachers who were experts in the field used different teaching strategies than competent teachers⁽²¹⁾. This showed that highly proficient science teachers go beyond basic teaching. They are more reflective and innovative, improving their practices to create a richer learning environment and achieve better student outcomes. This is also supported by another result: literacy can be successfully achieved through teacher training, multitiered support, and strong partnerships to promote inclusive education⁽²²⁾.

One study shows that learners demonstrated high participation in learning, and teachers’ strategies were consistent across demographic groups. While comprehension skills did not vary by age, education, or seniority, differences appeared by gender and location, with learners’ tendencies and challenges significantly linked to their performance⁽²³⁾. Effective, efficient teachers make learning fun and exciting by catering to all types of learners. They are teachers who create innovations and make teaching strategies their commitment to help students improve academic performance.

Table 6 presents the relationship between creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement, as measured by Spearman’s rho.

Table 6. The non-parametric correlation between creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement

Correlations				
			Creative Strategies	Pedagogical Enhancement
Spearman’s Rho	<i>Creative Strategies</i>	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.123
		Sig. (2-tailed)		.223
		N	100	100
	<i>Creative Strategies</i>	Correlation Coefficient	.123	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.223	
		N	100	1000

The correlation coefficient is 0.123, indicating a weak positive relationship. There is a minimal connection between the two: when creative strategies increase slightly, pedagogical enhancement also increases slightly. Furthermore, the p-value (Sig. = 0.223) is greater than the 0.05 significance level, indicating that the relationship is not statistically significant. Thus, there is no evidence that creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement are profoundly related in this study. The table shows that both are highly important in the science curriculum, but using creative strategies does not necessarily lead to greater pedagogical engagement among 100 DepEd science teachers in the Island of Panay, Philippines.

The study found that teaching creative thinking and problem-solving in higher education effectively prepares students to succeed across disciplines, especially in an AI-driven world, highlighting the importance of fostering creativity in modern education⁽²⁴⁾. Also, a problem-based learning (PBL) approach, when properly guided, improves students’ understanding of complex biological concepts. Well-structured, STEM-integrated PBL with guided inquiry improves students’ understanding of complex biology concepts⁽²⁵⁾. PBL is a creative strategy that allows students to explore real-life situations. This is also a pedagogical enhancement, as it allows science teachers to deliver high-quality instruction. Hence, knowledge of creative strategy and teachers’ creativity are essential. These are some of the best ways to improve science engagement among Filipino youth.

4 Conclusion

The study revealed that science teachers in the Island of Panay, Philippines, are young, highly educated, and actively engaged in teaching the basic education curriculum. Science teachers are aware of creative strategies but do not often use them in the classroom; these results imply a gap between knowledge and implementation. Creative strategies are crucial in the Philippine science curriculum; the need for more instructional materials is one of the main reasons the country has underperformed in various national and international assessments. In contrast, pedagogical enhancements are commonly employed by science teachers across all levels. The pedagogical enhancements are commonly used in knowledge exposure, collaborative learning, positive relationships, and problem-based learning. This implied that science teachers used structured instruction that supported students’ engagement and understanding. The Philippines’ service pedagogy has suffered for decades; many curricula have been introduced but have proven ineffective. Both creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement are essential for literacy. A profile of science teachers found that differences in educational qualifications, years of service, sex, and school type

slightly influence the use of creative strategies and pedagogical engagement. But teachers with doctoral degrees often used creative strategies, and the difference between the other categories is minimal. There is no significant relationship between creative strategies and pedagogical enhancement. Specific DepEd standards have some problems; teachers need help creating approaches tailored to students' levels. Thus, teachers have the authority to create critical approaches to science teaching and learning. The study suggests using the different creative strategies identified by DepEd and conducting a research study to determine their effectiveness in the science curriculum. These results benefit educators by offering engaging approaches that are essential to science pedagogy. Furthermore, these results recommended that higher education institutions (HEIs) offering preservice teacher courses should include creativity strategies and pedagogical enhancement in the curriculum to improve science literacy. In this way, as soon as they are ready, they are taught to develop strategies to increase the number of students who love science, take science into college, and become science enthusiasts. In this way, many will become doctors, nurses, engineers, scientists, researchers, and more. One common problem in science and technology in the Philippines is that very few people pursue careers in the field; thus, in the early years, learners must be encouraged to venture into science and technology, as it is always on trend.

In conclusion, science teachers in the Philippines demonstrate strong pedagogical skills but require further training to maximize creative strategies.

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